

P < NP

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March 21, 2021

Abstract:

The following is a proof that the time to obtain a suggested solution will always be short or equal to the time deciding whether there exist a solution. Methods used are set theory, functors and calculus of variations.

Introduction

Let it be a set -

$$A = \{a_1 \dots a_n\} \quad (1)$$

Define a condition on the set:

$$K : A \rightarrow B \quad (2)$$

Let $B = \{a_1 \dots a_m\}$ a subset of A which satisfy the condition K .

$$m < n.$$

Allocate:

$$K \rightarrow t_1 \quad (3)$$

Time in which the subset B was obtained after running the condition. Allow the elements of A to vary over time.

$$\Delta t : A \rightarrow A' \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta t : B \rightarrow B' \quad (5)$$

Let an isomorphism exist between the sets after the operation Δt . Define a functor on the subset B :

$$\varphi : \text{set} \rightarrow \text{Top} \quad (6)$$

In order to obtain an EL equation of the subset $L(B, B', t)$ on a topological space. Set the space to be complex analytical to ensure differentiation is possible at all time.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial B} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial B'} * \frac{d}{dt} = 0 \quad (7)$$

Or

$$B - B' * \Delta t = 0. \quad (8)$$

Since we allocated to obtaining the subset B the time $t(1)$ – we can write:

$$(t_1)B - B' * (t_1 + \Delta t) = 0 \quad (9)$$

For a given condition we impose on a set, which yield a subset to satisfy it, in order to ensure the subset to be a valid solution we are required to examine it will stay invariant under time translations after we operate a functor on it and switch to a topological space. In other words, the variations of the subset to vanish at border. One can say that the subset has to be close with respect to time. Thus, time obtaining a suggested solution will always to shorter than the time required deciding the existence of a solution the time of making a decision regarding the existence of a solution and obtaining the solution will be equal if the set is not varying over time. $\Delta t = 0$.

End of prove.